

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Simulating Resin Infusion for Manufacturing Sandwich- Structured Composites

Yi-Kai Kao, NTHU ROC

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Outline

- Introduction
- Methodologies
- Result
- Discussion
- Future work

Introduction-Sandwich Composites

Introduction-Review

✓C. H. Zhao, G. C. Zhang, and Y. B. Wu(2012)

The mold filling time is linearly reduced with an increase of the ratio of DM/Preform.

Ratio(DM/Preform) = 1

Ratio(DM/Preform) = 3/4

Ratio(DM/Preform) = 1/2

Ratio(DM/Preform) = 1/4

Introduction-Review

✓ E. Poodts, G. Minak, E. Dolcini, and L. Donati (2013)

1. The compaction pressure of the fibres (P_c) is a result of the balance of the external pressure (P_{ext}) and the resin pressure

it and stage of the process. The permeability coefficient (K) changes with the fiber volume fraction (V_f) according to the equation:

$$K(V_f) = GV_f^N$$

Zone	$K(V_f)$
A0	$5.059 \times 10^{-15} * V_f^{-16}$
A1	$6.412 \times 10^{-12} * V_f^{-4.8}$
B	$2.604 \times 10^{-10} * V_f^{-1}$
C	$3.676 \times 10^{-14} * V_f^{-10}$
D	$5.107 \times 10^{-19} * V_f^{-30}$

Methodologies-Equipment

Methodologies-Meshing

➤ Meshing & Property setting

- Length : 480 mm
- Width : 320 mm
- Height : 15 mm
- Mesh type: All-hexa mesh
- Quantity of mesh: 3817180

Methodologies- Fibre free Region

✓ J. Ni, Y. Zhao, L. J. Lee, and S. Nakamura(1997)

The average flow rate derived from Navier-Stokes equation is compared to the Darcy's flow rate to gather **Equivalent Permeability**.

$$K_{eq} = \frac{D^2}{32}$$

Cylindrical Channel

$$K_{eq} = \frac{1}{HW} \sum_{1,3,5,\dots} \frac{8}{n\pi\beta_n^3} \left[W - \frac{\sinh(\beta_n W)}{\beta_n} - \frac{1 - k\beta_n^2 - \frac{\sqrt{K}}{\alpha} \beta_n \sinh(\beta_n W) - \cosh(\beta_n W)}{\sinh(\beta_n W) + \frac{\sqrt{K}}{\alpha} \beta_n \cosh(\beta_n W)} \frac{\cosh(\beta_n W) - 1}{\beta_n} \right],$$

where $\beta_n = \frac{n\pi}{H}$

Rectangular Channel

Methodologies-Simulation Process setting

Material	(Equivalent) Permeability			Porosity	Viscosity (g/cm.sec)
	K11	K22	K33		
Distribution-medium	1.10E-09	8.20E-10	8.20E-10	0.42	
Cylindrical channel	1.25E-07	1.25E-07	1.25E-07	1	
Rectangular channel	7.69E-08	7.69E-08	7.69E-08	1	
Glass fabric1	1.60E-10	2.40E-12	5.00E-13	0.391	
Glass fabric2	2.40E-12	1.6E-10	5.00E-13	0.391	
Oil					0.89

Methodologies-Fibric Region(微觀-meso-巨觀)

Darcy's Law is used to describe the fibric region.

$$u = \frac{K}{\mu\phi} \nabla P$$

Methodologies-Software

Rhino can create, edit, analyze, document, render, animate, and translate NURBS curves, surfaces, and solids, point clouds, and polygon meshes. There are no limits on complexity, degree, or size beyond those of your hardware.

Moldex3D

Moldex3D Designer provides a complete series of powerful pre-processing tools, including automatic mesh generator and intelligent modeling wizards, to help users create True 3D mesh models efficiently and easily setup a variety of simulation conditions.

Results

Group1

Group2

Result-1(Top View)

Melt front time 10s(Experiment)

Melt front time 10s(Simulation)

Melt front time 20s(Experiment)

Melt front time 20s(Simulation)

Result-1(Bottom View)

Melt front time 90s(Experiment)

Melt front time 90s(Simulation)

Melt front time 120s(Experiment)

Melt front time 120s(Simulation)

Result-2(Top View)

Melt front time 15s(Experiment)

Melt front time 15s(Simulation)

Melt front time 30s(Experiment)

Melt front time 30s(Simulation)

Result-2(Bottom View)

Melt front time 45s(Experiment)

Melt front time 45s(Simulation)

Melt front time 90s(Experiment)

Melt front time 90s(Simulation)

Discussion

- The flow pattern of simulation is similar to the real experiment of two groups.
- Comparing with the traditional method, the method this work provides is able to describe the resin flow pattern during the manufacturing of sandwich composites.
- This method is also flexible to modularly achieve various combinations of different kinds of fabrics and/or cores. Owing to this feature, the final product's quality can be predicted.

Future work

- Doing experiment and simulation of combinations of different kinds of fibers and/or cores.
- Improve the process by adjust the controllable parameter through the simulation